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RISK TAKERS VS RISK AVERTERS – A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INVESTORS’ BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

The risk taking attitude of the investors purely depends on the amount or rate of return expected by the investors. If any investor who is aspiring for higher return out the investment made obviously the investor is having high risk taking attitude. Higher return expectation leads to higher the risk taken and lower return expectation leads to lower the risk taken. An investor can either be a risk taker (aggressive or moderate) or risk averter (conservative). The Indian financial market comprises of risky financial products as well as the risk free financial products. It is choice of the investor to prefer either risky or risk free financial products. Now-a-days a shift in the investment preference of investors from risk free financial products to risk associated financial products can be evidenced in the emerging economies like India. An attempt has been made in this study to discriminate the investors in to risk takers and risk averters. A further attempt has also been made to rank the investors with respect to various factors influencing the investors in prioritizing their objective.

Key words: Risk takers, Risk averters, Discriminant analysis, Garrett’s Ranking

Introduction

Indian financial market has provided a platform to the investors to park their surplus funds. Various types of financial products are now available in the Indian financial market suiting the different needs of the investors. Now an investor has got the own choice in selection of financial product to deploy the funds. Now-a-days the financial market is well informed with respect to the financial products subsequently the investors are also highly informative about the market conditions. Now the market intermediaries and credit rating agencies are providing plenty of assistance and support to the investors in selecting a particular financial product for investment. According to the present system in the market, it is highly possible for an investor to enjoy the various monetary and non monetary benefits by the way of making investment in the various financial assets. Individual investors are driven to pool their surplus funds in the equity and derivative market in recent times. Risk is one of the major determinants for making investment. Before going to invest in certain financial asset it is highly necessary to calculate the quantum of risk involved in it. Under the risk aspect the financial products are categorized into High risk products, moderate risk products and low/no risk products. The investors those who prefer high risk financial products are called as aggressive investor and the investors those who prefer moderate risk financial products are called as moderate investors. Finally the investors who prefer low/no risk financial products are called as conservative investors. The aggressive investors will have a high a high risk taking attitude, the moderate investors will have a moderate risk taking attitude and the conservative investors will a low or no risk taking attitude. Ultimately the aggressive and moderate investors are called as risk takers where as the conservative investors are called as risk averters. The risk taking attitude of the investors purely depends on the amount or rate of return expected by the investors. If any investor who is aspiring for higher return out the investment made obviously the investor is having high risk taking attitude. Higher return expectation leads to higher the risk taken and lower return expectation leads to lower the risk taken. An investor can either be a risk taker (aggressive or moderate) or risk averter (conservative). The Indian financial market comprises of risky financial products as well as the risk free financial products. It is choice of the investor to prefer either risky or risk free financial products. Now-a-days a shift in the investment preference of investors from risk free financial products to risk associated financial products can be evidenced in the emerging economies like India.

Objectives

- To know the preference of the individual households in selecting the investment avenues with respect to their investment objectives
- To examine the factors in discriminating between the risk taker and risk avoider.

Hypothesis

- Null Hypothesis H0: There is no significant difference in terms of means among the predictor variables
- Alternate Hypothesis H1: There is S significant difference in terms of means among the predictor variables

Scope of the study:

The study is limited to

- Attitude toward investment.
- Preference in terms of selection

Statistical tools and analysis:

- Garret's Ranking
- Discriminant Analysis

Limitations of the study

- ❖ This study has been limited by time and cost factors.
- ❖ Since analyzes has been made from the information given by the respondents, the accuracy of the findings are depended on the quality of the respondents.
- ❖ This sample refers only to a set of population i.e. a set of prospective investor.
- ❖ The sample size of 80 is only a small percentage of total investing public, therefore it is only a representation report based on the sample study.
- ❖ The sample is confirmed to Chennai city only.
- ❖ The answers provided by the respondents may not be genuine.
- ❖ The study is confined to very little respondents. The implications so found are specific to that unit and any generalization may not be possible.

Analysis & Interpretation

Garett's Ranking

TABLE 1: Objective Priority While Investing:

Objectives	Rank
Regular income oriented	1
Growth oriented	2
Short term profit seeking	3
Long term profit seeking	4
Balanced aspect	5
Tax saving purpose	6

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 1 it is inferred that major respondents give priority for regularly income oriented, growth oriented, short and long term profit seeking, followed by balanced aspect and tax saving purpose.

DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS:

From the table-2, it is inferred that the mean for age group of risk taker is 7, whereas for risk avoiders its 5.59. The mean for level of income for risk taker is 6.44, whereas for risk avoiders it is 6.38. For the characteristic of years of experience the mean for risk avoiders is 7.33 while it is 6.62 for risk takers. The mean for awareness of market is 7.56 for risk avoiders whereas it is 7.44 for risk takers. The mean for conservative attitude is 6.88 risk takers, whereas it is 5.36 for risk avoiders.

TABLE 2 GROUP STATISTICS:

Whether you are taking risk in your investment		Mean	Std. Deviation	Valid N (listwise)	
				Unweighted	Weighted
Yes	Age group	7.00	1.265	16	16.000
	Level of income	6.44	.892	16	16.000
	Year of experience	6.62	1.147	16	16.000
	Awareness of market sentiments	7.44	1.315	16	16.000
	Conservative attitude	6.88	1.360	16	16.000
No	Age group	5.59	1.109	64	64.000
	Level of income	6.38	1.315	64	64.000
	Year of experience	7.33	1.085	64	64.000
	Awareness of market sentiments	7.56	.906	64	64.000
	Conservative attitude	5.36	1.252	64	64.000
Total	Age group	5.88	1.267	80	80.000
	Level of income	6.39	1.238	80	80.000
	Year of experience	7.19	1.126	80	80.000
	Awareness of market sentiments	7.54	.993	80	80.000
	Conservative attitude	5.66	1.405	80	80.000

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 2 it is clearly stated that, there are two groups namely risk takers and risk avoiders which are compared on five basic characteristics such as

- Age group
- Level of income
- Year of experience
- Awareness of market sentiments
- Conservative attitude

TABLE 3 TESTS OF EQUALITY OF GROUP MEAN:

	Wilks' Lambda	F	df1	df2	Sig.
Age group	.800	19.464	1	78	.000
Level of income	1.000	.032	1	78	.858
Year of experience	.937	5.259	1	78	.025
Awareness of market sentiments	.997	.201	1	78	.655
Conservative attitude	.811	18.132	1	78	.000

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 3 the characteristic namely age group (p = 0.000), year of experience (p = .025), conservative attitude (p = 0.000) which is less than assumed level 0.05 it has significant difference whereas the other two variable doesn't have any significant difference.

TABLE 4 POOLED WITHIN-GROUPS MATRICES(CORRELATION):

		Age group	Level of income	Year of experience	Awareness of market sentiments	Conservative attitude
	Age group	1.000	.530	.210	.063	.330
	Level of income	.530	1.000	.382	.242	.536
	Year of experience	.210	.382	1.000	.501	.181
	Awareness of market sentiments	.063	.242	.501	1.000	.191
	Conservative attitude	.330	.536	.181	.191	1.000

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 4 it is inferred that the correlation between any pair of variable doesn't exceed 0.75 hence there is no problem of multicollinearity.

TABLE 5 EIGENVALUES:

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	1.093	100.0	100.0	.639

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 5 the canonical correlation is the simple correlation. The value is 0.693 and the square value is (.693² = .4803) which means 49% variance in the discriminating model between the risk taker/avoiders with respect to above 5 characteristics.

TABLE 6 WILKS' LAMBDA:

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	Df	Sig.
1	.592	39.641	5	.000

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 6 it is inferred that the value of wilks' Lambda is 0.592 which is obtained similarly using one-way Anova .Hence the value falls between 0 and 1 which is at the significant level.the statistical test is carried with chi square which value 39.641.also the p value is 0.00,it is inferred that discriminant function is significant.

TABLE 7 STANDARDIZED CANONICAL DISCRIMINANT FUNCTION COEFFICIENTS:

Characteristics	Function 1
Age group	.788
Level of income	-.647
Year of experience	-.420
Awareness of market sentiments	.119

Characteristics	Function 1
Age group	.788
Level of income	-.647
Year of experience	-.420
Awareness of market sentiments	.119
Conservative attitude	.721

INFERENCE: From the table 7 it is inferred that the age group(0.788) is the most important characteristics which discriminates between risk takers and risk avoiders, followed by remaining 4 characteristics namely conservative attitude(0.721),awareness of market sentiment(0.119), years of experience(-0.420),level of income (-0.647) respectively.

TABLE 8 STRUCTURE MATRIX:

	Function
Age group	.601
Conservative attitude	.580
Year of experience	-.312
Awareness of market sentiments	-.061
Level of income	.024

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 8 it is inferred that the age group (0.601) is the most discriminate characteristics, followed by conservative attitude (0.580) which is considered to 2nd important characteristics, followed by the remaining characteristics level of income (0.24), awareness of market sentiment (-0.61), years of experience (-0.312).

TABLE 9 CANONICAL DISCRIMINANT FUNCTION COEFFICIENTS:

	Function
Age group	.691
Level of income	-.520
Year of experience	-.383
Awareness of market sentiments	.119
Conservative attitude	.566
(Constant)	-2.084

Source :COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 9 the higher eigenvalue and desirable value is age group (0.691), followed by conservative attitude (0.566), awareness of market sentiment (0.119), years of experience (-0.383), level of income (-0.520).

TABLE 10 FUNCTIONS AT GROUP CENTROIDS:

Whether you are taking risk in your investment	Function
	1
Yes	1.641
No	-4.10

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: from the table 10 it is inferred that major respondents fall under risk avoiders (-4.10), Risk taker are numbered in (1.641) indicating respondent with value above 0 are risk takers and respondent with value below 0 falls under risk avoiders.

TABLE 11 PRIOR PROBABILITIES FOR GROUPS:

Whether you are taking risk in your investment	Prior	Cases Used in Analysis	
		Unweighted	Weighted
Yes	.500	16	16.000
No	.500	64	64.000
Total	1.000	80	80.000

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 11 it is inferred that out of 80 respondents 64 respondents are risk avoiders whereas 16 respondents out of 80 respondents are risk takers.

TABLE 12 CLASSIFICATION RESULTS:

Whether you are taking risk in your investment			Predicted Group Membership		Total
			Yes	No	
Original	Count	Yes	13	3	16
		No	9	55	64
	%	Yes	81.2	18.8	100.0
		No	14.1	85.9	100.0
Cross-validated ^a	Count	Yes	12	4	16
		No	11	53	64
	%	Yes	75.0	25.0	100.0
		No	17.2	82.8	100.0

a. Cross validation is done only for those cases in the analysis. In cross validation, each case is classified by the functions derived from all cases other than that case.

b. 85.0% of original grouped cases correctly classified.

c. 81.3% of cross-validated grouped cases correctly classified.

Source: COMPUTED DATA

INFERENCE: From the table 11 it is inferred that out of 16 respondents who are actually risk takers it is predicted 13 are risk takers similarly out of 64 actually risk avoiders respondents it is predicted that 55 are risk avoiders.

Conclusion

As far as the investors' preference in selecting their investment avenue is concerned, the prioritization is given to regular income followed by growth and short term gain indicating the importance given to the risk free investment avenue. Further it is highlighted that there are certain key factors such as age group, level of income, experience, awareness of market and conservative attitude play a major role in dividing the investors into risk taker and risk avoider. By applying discriminant analysis it is found that age group has emerged the most important factor to be considered in terms of discriminating between risk taker and risk avoider category followed by conservative attitude and level of market awareness.

References

1. Warne, D. P. (2012). Investment Behaviour of Individual Investor in Stock Market. *International Journal of Research in Finance & Marketing, 2(2)*.
2. Bennet, E., Selvam, M., Indhumathi, G., Ramkumar, R. R., & Karpagam, V. (2011). Factors Influencing Retail Investors Attitude Towards Investing In Equity Stocks: A Study In Tamil Nadu '.
3. Vyas, R. (2012). Mutual Fund Investor's Behaviour and Perception In Indore City. *Researchers World: Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce, 3(1)*
4. Karmarkar, M. (2001). Investment Behavior of Household sector-A study of a Rural Block in West Bengal. *The Indian Journal of Commerce, 54, 58*.
5. Sehgal, S., Sood, G. S., & Rajput, N. (2009). Investor Sentiment in India: A Survey. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective, 13(2), 13-23*.
6. Chandra, A., & Kumar, R. (2012). Factors Influencing Indian Individual Investor Behaviour: Survey Evidence.